

PRE-UNIVERSITY EDUCATIONAL CYCLE AND QUALITY OF EDUCATION

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Abstract

Quality basic education is a key to producing capable human capital for the sustainability of intercontinental contest. Open TIMSS database that provides profile of 42 countries on various predictor-variables was analyzed using the Association and Cluster Analyses. A regression model was used to predict mean score. Mean score, the length of pre-school sub-cycle, total length of pre-university sub-cycle and literacy rate of a country are associated with each other. It was also found out that basic education plays a crucial role in physical, political, cultural and economic dimensions of a country. The focus therefore is on strengthening the capacities of the students to act progressively on their own behalf through the acquisition of relevant knowledge, useful skills and desirable attitudes, eventually helping to create for themselves and others, asylum of safety, security and healthy relations which could be actualized through a protracted pre-university education.

Keywords: *Quality Basic Education, Association and Cluster Analysis, Protracted Pre-University Education*

Introduction

The transformation of the world into a global society thereby bridging the gaps of intercontinental boundaries for free trade brings out the evident economic and industrial contest among countries. Countries have come to recognize that economic and political survival rely mainly on competitive advantage a country dominates over others (Ngwudike, 2009). Consequently, a country needs to produce a large puddle of intelligent, skilled and competent human resources in order to sustain this competition.

The abundance of this breed of workforce depends on the quality of students a country produces through the realization of basic education, basically in the core area of mathematics and science. Chubb and Moe (1990) asserted that mathematics proficiency is a vehicle for producing a skilled workforce needed to sustain a nation's competitive edge in today's global economy and is important to the future of sophisticated technology and competition worldwide.

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The role of mathematics and science in global struggle kindles numerous countries to turn to international assessments conducted every 4 years by the International Association for the Evaluation of Educational Achievement (IEA) through the famous Trends in International Mathematics and Science Study (TIMSS) as a way of measuring their future competitive edge. TIMSS is an intercontinental assessment firstly administered in 1995 that provides crossnational achievement of fourth- and eighth-grade students around the world in mathematics and science (Gonzales et al., 2004).

The 2003 TIMSS revealed that the archipelagic Philippines (RP), where the length of BEC cycle is one of the shortest in the world, is lagging behind other Asian nations to name a few: Singapore, Taiwan, South Korea, Hongkong, Japan, which ranked 1st, 2nd, 3rd, 4th, and 5th, respectively. Low quality of basic education in the country caused by ineffectiveness of math and science instruction, lack of books and inadequacy of physical plants and facilities is the principal cause of the thwarting achievement of students particularly in science and mathematics (William, 2004).

With the utilization of open TIMSS database, this current study intended to determine the influence of lengths of schooling in TIMSS participating countries and their profile in terms of their Literacy Rate (LR), Gross Domestic Product (GDP), Malnutrition Rate (MR), Peace Index (PI) and number of English as a Second Language (ESL) speakers on the promotion of quality basic education.

Brief Literature Review

The importance attached to basic education is underscored by the Education for All (EFA) movement that seeks to provide basic education for all. In the Philippines, this movement is given support by our local policies and seeks to achieve its major goals by the year 2015. “The Philippines has put in place major governance reforms that make the policy environment favourable for Education for All 2015 Goals” (Caoli-Rodriguez, 2007).

In the study of Felipe on an Actual Case of Lengthening A Sub-Cycle Which Was Not Followed By The Improvement That Was Expected: The Philippine Case, he averred that, in the Philippines, there have been indications that adding more years may just be a waste of time and resources. Thirty-four years ago, the Department of Education of that period already reported that Grade 6 pupils, apparently (as measured by achievement tests), knew just a little bit more than Grade 5 pupils (Survey of Outcomes of Elementary Education, or SOUTELE, 1976 as cited by Felipe 2010).

Research Design and Quantitative Framework

A file for each TIMSS-participating country was constructed, consisting of the country’s mean TIMSS test scores and the corresponding UNESCO data on educational cycles. The test data were taken from the summary statistics report of the TIMSS International Study Center, Boston College, the center of TIMMS studies. The UNESCO data were taken from its website.

The current investigation made use of the TIMSS (*year unknown*) database provided. The data supply the scores of 4th and 8th graders among 42 participating countries, their respective lengths of pre-school, elementary, and high school sub-cycles, total length of pre-university sub-cycles and their respective Literacy Rate (LR), Gross Domestic Product (GDP), Malnutrition Rate (MR), Peace Index (PI) and number of citizens who speak English as a Second Language (ESL) on quality education.

Initial runs on the data included Association Analysis (AA) utilizing the Apriori Principle, as well as Cluster Observation (CO) and Regression Analysis (RA) to determine the reliability of the analyses eventually finding out which among the variables are good determinants on the promotion of quality education.

The math and science raw scores of 4th and 8th graders among participating countries were used as dependent variables in the statistical analyses with lengths of BEC cycle in TIMSS participating countries and their LR, GDP, MR, PI, ESL were used as determinants. The results of analyses undertaken, with the aid of MINITAB statistical package, are shown below.

Results

The Association Analysis (AA) utilizing the Apriori Principle, as presented in Table 1, revealed that mean score of 8th graders (M8) and literacy rate (LR) of a country are associated with each other (*minsup* < 22). This implies that the higher the mean score of 8th graders, the higher the LR. The CO, and RA shown in Table 2 and in Box 1, respectively disclose the same findings. The country's quality of education at any level, therefore, is significantly related with the achievement of high school students.

Table 1 Association Analysis Utilizing Apriori Principle and Rejection of Item Set

Items Sets					
Set 1	Count	Set 2	Count	Set 3	Count
Mean Score – 8 th Grade [M8]	23	M8, PS	18	M8, PS, ES	9
Length of Pre-school Sub-Cycle (<i>in years</i>) [PS]	26	M8, ES	13	M8, PS, US	16
Length of Elementary Sub-Cycle (<i>in years</i>) [ES]	28	M8, US	18	M8, PS, LR	18
Length of High School Sub-cycle (<i>in years</i>) [HS]	17	M8, LR	22	M8, ES, US	9
Total Length of Pre-University Sub-Cycle (<i>in years</i>) [US]	25	PS, ES	15	M8, ES, LR	13
Mean Score – 4 th Grade [M8]	13	PS, US	23	M8, US, LR	17
Literacy Rate [LR]	29	PS, LR	22	PS, ES, US	14
Gross Domestic Product [GDP]	8	ES, US	16	PS, US, LR	19
Malnutrition Rate [MR]	6	ES, LR	17	ES, US, LR	11
Peace Index [PI]	14	US, LR	23		
English as Second Language Speakers [ESL]	3				
<i>Minsup</i> = 21					

Note: Only the highlighted items are accepted ($I_s > \text{minsup}$).

The associations between the length of pre-school sub-cycle (PS), total length of pre-university sub-cycle (US) and LR are also perceptible (*minsup* < 22). Cluster 3 in Table 2 possesses the highest PS (3) and LR (99) while the Cluster 2 holds the highest US (6.55). It is therefore asserted that the longer the students are indulged in pre-school education, the higher the LR; and so as if they spend many years learning before entering university, and vice versa.

Table 2 Cluster Centroids

Variable	Cluster1	Cluster2	Cluster3	Grand Center
Mean,8th	480.4762	438.7500	509.0000	461.2857
Length o	2.9048	2.5500	3.0000	2.7381
Length o	5.5714	5.4000	6.0000	5.5000
Length o	6.4762	6.5500	6.0000	6.5000
Total le	14.9524	14.5000	15.0000	14.7381
Mean 4th	516.7483	485.3643	519.0000	501.8571
Literacy	94.4319	91.1335	99.0000	92.9700
GDP	424222.1429	404200.0195	1.425628E+07	744022.3902
Malnutri	0.0681	0.0810	0.0500	0.0738
Peace In	1.8308	1.7110	2.0150	1.7781
English-	1165229.3810	1.075979E+07	2.154236E+08	1.083546E+07

A closer look at the regression equation to predict the mean score of 4th and 8th graders presented inside the box as shown below provides that the lower the malnutrition rate of the country, the higher is its mean score; the lower is its peace index, the higher is the mean score; and, the lower the number of English as Second Language (ESL) speakers, the higher is the mean score.

The R–Sq of 43. 6% means that about half of the variation in mean scores of eight graders only one-fourth of the mean score of 4th graders difference can be explained by the regression model.

THE REGRESSION EQUATION IS:	
<p>Mea 8th grade = 295 + 7.5 Length of Pre-school Sub-Cycle(- 4.71 Length of Elementary Sub-cycle + 2.75 Literacy rate +0.000022 GDP + 52 Malnutrition Rate - 50.9 Peace Index_1 -0.000001 English-First</p> <p>R-Sq = 43.6%</p>	<p>Mean 4th grade = 383 + 7.44 Length of Pre-school Sub-Cycle(+ 1.22 Literacy rate +0.000013 GDP - 28 Malnutrition Rate - 7.5 Peace Index_1 -0.000001 English-First</p> <p>R-Sq = 25.4%</p>

Discussions and conclusions

The Association Analysis reveals that mean score of 8th graders (M8), the length of pre-school sub-cycle (PS), total length of pre-university sub-cycle (US) and literacy rate (LR) of a country are associated with each other. Thus, the higher the mean score of 8th graders, the higher is the LR of a nation. Moreover, the longer the students are indulged in pre-school education, the higher also is the LR; and so as if they spend many years

learning before entering university, and vice versa Felipe (2010), Padua (2011). Cluster Observation and regression analysis supported the reliability of the present findings.

A greater percentage of the variance in student achievement, 43.6% can be explained by the regression model. Significant predictor-variables offer important insights on how schools can further improve student performance. For one, as a matter of policy, longer basic schooling cycle could be pushed through to promote quality basic education in the country.

The quality and length of basic education of a country therefore predict its literacy rating in the entirety. The ability of the citizenry in comprehending written texts and oral words, in expressing ideas and opinions, in computing printed and written materials and in making decisions and solving problems associated with varying contexts as what literacy is all about is fundamental in pre-university formal education panorama. Enabling students to learn basic knowledge and skills at a longer schooling span may lead to consequently developing their skills and potentials to the fullest so as to participate wholly in their respective community and wider society in the future; thus becoming one amongst the intelligent, skilled and competent human capital who could sustain a country's edge over others.

The regression equation, on the other hand, reveals that the lower the malnutrition rate, peace index and number of English as Second Language (ESL) speakers of the country, the higher is the mean score. The quality of education of a country therefore could be measured through availability of healthy, well-nourished citizens who are ready to participate and learn, and environment that provides security. This definition allows for an understanding of education as a complex system embedded in a political, cultural and economic context.

Conclusively, basic education plays an important role in providing the basis for a healthy life, peace and order stability and a successful formal schooling experience. In all aspects, quality education means the realization of physical, political, cultural and economic functions. The focus therefore is on strengthening the capacities of the students to act progressively on their own behalf through the acquisition of relevant knowledge, useful skills and desirable attitudes, eventually helping to create for themselves and others, asylum of safety, security and healthy relations. This could be actualized through a protracted pre-university education.

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